

CONNECTING WOMEN IN DIGITAL

2.4 ANNUAL WOMEN IN DIGITAL INDEX AND SCOREBOARD V1

WP2

IDC

Funded by
the European Union

Technical references

Project Acronym	WIDCON
Project Title	Connecting Women in Digital
Document nr. and title	D2.4 Annual Women in Digital (WiD) Index and Scoreboard V1
Work Package	WP2 – Data collection and index development
Dissemination level	Public
Lead beneficiary	IDC
Contributors	Leonardo Freitas (IDC), Martina Longo (IDC)
Due date	31.12.2025
Actual submission date	16.12.2025

ABSTRACT

The Annual Women in Digital (WiD) Index and Scoreboard V1 document provides a dataset containing the WiD Index scores for the EU and individual Member States. This document serves as a companion to the WiD Index dataset (.xls) featured in D2.2 WiD index foundational data and survey findings, providing insights into the methodology and limitations underlying the development of the Index, including the use of primary and secondary data and the country scoring approach. The Index and scoreboard aim to track and benchmark the participation of girls and women across the digital pipeline, from the beginning of their education in STEM to leadership roles in the digital sector. This document also includes a section that guides users through the online dashboard visualizations, available for consulting and interacting with the Index at <https://index.widigital.eu/index/>. A detailed analysis of country-level Index scores will be presented in D5.1 – State of WiD report.

KEYWORDS

Data, Survey, Member States, Index, Methodology, Framework, Gender, Limitations, STEM Education, ICT Education, ICT Specialists, ICT Leadership, EU, Digital, Web, Dashboards, Interactive

History of changes

Version	Author	Partner	Date	Description of changes
v.1.0	Leonardo Freitas (IDC), Martina Longo (IDC)		09/09/2025	First iteration of the methodological note after the completion of the Index.
v1.1	Leonardo Freitas (IDC), Martina Longo (IDC)	Joana Xhemali (EVTA)	05/10/2025	Second iteration of the methodological note, incorporating intersectionality comments from EVTA; Formatting changes.
V1.2	Leonardo Freitas (IDC), Martina Longo (IDC)	Ilker Dermikol (UPC), Sebastian Mayer (EITD)	15/10/2025	Final formatting changes, sources clarifications and alignment with the quantitative Index deliverable.
V2.1	Liubba El Hadi Hamed (BLU)		28/10/2025	Provided feedback on weighting

Version	Author	Partner	Date	Description of changes
				explanations and data limitations sections.
V2.2	Martina Longo, Leonardo Freitas (IDC)		04/12/2025	Section and explanatory comments on the dashboard added. Document renamed as D2.4 Annual WiD Index and scoreboard V1
D2.4 V1_v01	Martina Longo (IDC)	Sebastian Meyer (28D), Mattia Trino (BDVA)	16/12/2025	Incorporating minor feedback from reviewers on image quality and final editing

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1. About the Women in Digital Index

1.1. Purpose of the Index

The Women in Digital Index (WiD Index) is a data-driven tool developed by the *Connecting Women in Digital* consortium to monitor the progression of women through education and careers in ICT across the EU and selected benchmark countries. It integrates primary and secondary data along with expert insights to identify gaps and drop-off points along the digital pipeline, from STEM and ICT education to leadership roles in the sector. By comparing national initiatives and outcomes, the index aims to highlight gaps, showcase best practices, and best performers across Member States and benchmarked countries.

Strategic purpose and identified stakeholders of the WiD index are detailed in D1.1, WIDCON Playbook.

1.1.1. How to navigate the WiD Index Women in Digital (WiD) Index Foundational Data and Survey Findings Dataset

Deliverable 2.2 – Women in Digital Index and Survey Findings presents a comprehensive dataset that aggregates results for all 27 EU Member States and benchmarked countries. It includes:

- A Table of Contents with direct hyperlinks to each section of the document.
- The full list of metrics that compose the Index, organized by phase and accompanied by brief descriptions.
- The Women in Digital Country Ranking for EU Member States and benchmarked countries, showing total Index scores and aggregated results by phase - from STEM to Leadership - for all 31 countries in scope.

- The EU minimum-maximum bands for each Index metric (see Section 2 – Methodology behind the Index – for details on the Index structure and step-by-step calculation process).
- Individual country data sheets, offering detailed scoring by metric and phase for each of the 31 countries. These sheets can be consulted independently or alongside the overall country ranking for benchmarking purposes.

The following sections of this methodological note provide key information on the Index’s structure, metrics, methodology, data sources, limitations, and mitigation strategies.

1.1.2. The WiD Index Structure and Metrics

The pillars and metrics featured in the WiD Index are constructed combining publicly available statistical datasets, the dedicated 2025 Women in Digital survey, secondary research and the sourcing of national and policy initiatives at Leadership phase, featured in deliverable 2.1 “Overview of national actions”.

The Women in Digital Pipeline featured in the WiD has been divided in four principal phases that reflect core stages of an individual’s education and career paths. These are:

- **STEM**
 - Stages: Primary and Secondary Education
 - Core points: participation of girls in STEM subjects
- **ICT**
 - Stages: Higher Education, I-VET
 - Core points: participation of women in ICT and related subjects
- **DIGITAL**

- Stages: Early-to-middle career
- Core points: participation of women in digital roles
- **LEADERSHIP**
 - Stage: Leadership
 - Core points: participation of women in leadership roles

Figure 1 Representation of the Women in Digital Pipeline and core stages

Source: Connecting Women in Digital – D1.1 WIDCON Playbook

1.1.2.1. Index Framework: Final list of metrics comprising the Index

The WiD Index tracks the Women in Digital pipeline across its key stages, using a set of quantitative metrics designed to identify critical gaps in retaining women's participation. The goal is to generate actionable insights and recommendations to close these gaps and enhance women's engagement throughout the pipeline.

Below is the final list of metrics included in the WiD Index, along with their descriptions and sources:

STEM Phase: Girls' participation and achievement in STEM education and subjects in secondary education, including vocational education and training. This stage measures early engagement, growth of interest and achievement as a foundation for later ICT and digital higher education and careers. It helps identify gender disparities in STEM performance at the age typically associated with the end of compulsory education. This comparison not only highlights existing systemic inequalities but also reveals successful education policies or cultural factors that support girls in science and math, offering valuable practices that can be adapted or replicated. Note: Due to a low availability of quantitative data, STEM performance in primary education will be covered through qualitative insights via the Forum and dedicated workshops.

Table 1 Quantitative metrics included in the STEM phase

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
ST1. Girls' performance in Science in secondary education across countries	Secondary Education	Average science scores of girls students aged 15 by EU Member States and benchmarking countries (subject to availability).	OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), 2022	Five years sampling frequency. Sample is consistent but focuses on 15-year-old students only, which may not adequately represent total population. Only OECD member countries are included within the perimeter.
ST2. Girls' performance in Math in secondary education across countries.	Secondary Education	Average math scores of girls students aged 15 by EU Member States and benchmarking countries	OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), 2022	Five years sampling frequency. Sample is consistent but focuses on 15-year-old students only, which may not adequately represent total population. Only OECD member

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
		(subject to availability).		countries are included within the perimeter.
ST3. Girls' performance in PISA in Science relative to boys	Secondary education	Difference between average science scores of girls and boys students aged 15 by EU Member States and benchmarking countries (subject to availability).	OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), 2022	Five years sampling frequency. Sample is consistent but focuses on 15-year-old students only, which may not adequately represent total population. Only OECD member countries are included within the perimeter.
ST4. Girls' performance in PISA in Math relative to boys	Secondary education	Difference between average math scores of girls and boys students aged 15 by EU Member States and benchmarking countries (subject to availability).	OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), 2022	Five years sampling frequency. Sample is consistent but focuses on 15-year-old students only, which may not adequately represent total population. Only OECD member countries are included within the perimeter.
ST5. Girls in upper secondary STEM IVET (ISCED 3) programmes	I-VET	Participation of girls in upper secondary vocational STEM programme education (ISCED 3 – Subject to availability of STEM pathways in	Eurostat: educ_uae_ent02, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months.

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
		specific countries).		

ICT Phase: Participation of women in ICT and related subjects in tertiary, initial vocational training (I-VET), postgraduate and doctoral education. These indicators assess the availability of highly qualified women candidates for specialised roles in ICT and digital.

Table 2 Quantitative metrics included in the ICT phase

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
IT1. Women bachelor ICT graduates (ISCED Level 6)	Higher Education	Proportion of women from total ICT bachelor graduates by each EU Member State and benchmarking countries.	Eurostat: educ_uae_grad02, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months for Eurostat.
IT2. Women with an ICT master of science (ISCED Level 7)	Higher Education	Proportion of women from all graduates with a master degree in ICT by each EU Member State and benchmarking countries.	Eurostat: educ_uae_grad02, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months for Eurostat.
IT4. Women with a PhD in ICT-related fields (ISCED Level 8)	Higher Education	Proportion of women among all ICT Doctoral graduates by each EU Member State and benchmarking countries.	Eurostat: educ_uae_grad02, 2023	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).
IT4. Women enrolled in ICT-related post	I-VET	Proportion of women with an ICT related post-secondary non-tertiary vocational education	Women in Digital proprietary survey, 2025	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
secondary I-VET		and/or short-cycle tertiary education, vocational/professional by each EU Member State and benchmarking countries.		represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).

Digital Phase: Women's participation in ICT and digital roles is examined through indicators such as employment rates, the proportion of female ICT specialists, enrolment in continuous vocational training, the gender pay gap, and contractual conditions during early to mid-career stages. This phase highlights whether women are progressing beyond entry-level positions, gaining the necessary experience and training opportunities, potential barriers to progression and finally the retention rate of women in digital.

Table 3 Quantitative metrics included in the Digital phase

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
DG1. Employed women with an ICT education	Early-to-middle career	Proportion of employed women with an ICT education.	Eurostat: isoc_ski_itsex, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months
DG2. Women ICT specialists	Early-to-middle career	Proportion of women from all ICT specialists.	Eurostat: isoc_sks_itsps, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months.
DG3. Women in ICT continuous vocational trainings (CVET)	Early-to-middle career	Proportion of women enrolled in ICT continuous vocational trainings vs men (CVT) (e.g. upskilling and reskilling programmes).	Women in Digital proprietary survey, 2025	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
DG4. Perception of gender pay gap in ICT	Early-to-middle career	Proportion of women indicating pay disparity as a key challenge for women's retention and career progression in ICT and digital.	Women in Digital proprietary survey, 2025	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).
DG5. Gender pay gap in ICT	Early-to-middle career	Percentage difference between average gross hourly earnings of men and women ICT professionals, expressed as a percentage of men's earnings.	Eurostat: earn_gr_gpgr2, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months.

Leadership Phase: Women's participation in ICT and digital leadership, both in technical leadership roles and as top executives or board members in ICT companies. Indicators at this stage are crucial for understanding the extent to which women have broken through the “glass ceiling” and achieved leadership parity, influencing strategic decision-making and innovation.

Table 4 Quantitative metrics included in the Leadership phase

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
LD1. Time taken for women to reach leadership positions	Leadership	Average duration (in years) required for women to advance from ICT entry-level positions to ICT leadership roles.	Women in Digital proprietary survey, 2025	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).

Metric	Stage	Definition	Data source	Limitations
LD2. Women in technical leadership roles	Leadership	Proportion of women with Director level and above in ICT roles.	Women in Digital proprietary survey, 2025	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).
LD3. Women in leadership roles in ICT companies	Leadership	Average proportion of women in a leadership role (Director level and above) in ICT companies.	Women in Digital proprietary survey, 2025	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).
LD.4 Key long-term inhibitors to ICT leadership	Leadership	Combined proportion of top challenges to women's retention and career progression in ICT and digital: work life balance, possibility of career advancement, access to skills development.	Women in Digital proprietary survey, 2025	Total sample is consistent to show a trend but may not represent total population. Countries with small sample sizes are highlighted and marked with an asterisk (*).

Enabling Environment: This underlying additional phase outside the ICT and digital pipeline includes metrics linked to broader societal and structural factors that influence women's participation and success beyond - but also directly influence - ICT and digital roles by country, from basic digital skills to overall women participation in the workforce

Table 5 Quantitative metrics included in the Enabling Environment

Metric	Definition	Data source	Limitations
EE1. Women with basic or above basic overall digital skills	Proportion of women with basic or above basic overall digital skills over total women population	Eurostat: eq_dskl07, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months
EE2. Women currently unemployed	Proportion of women between 20-64 currently not employed	Eurostat: lfsi_emp_a, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months
EE3. Women with children employment rate	Proportion of women with children employed	Eurostat: lfst_hheredty, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months
EE4. Contractual conditions of women	Proportion of women with full-time employment	Eurostat: lfsa_epgais, 2023	Lag from date of data collection to access of around 24 months
EE5. Member State Monitoring - Policy initiative score	Average score achieved by each EU country in national initiatives promoting gender equality and women's participation in the digital sector	Connecting Women in Digital, D2.1 Overview of national actions, 2025	List of initiatives gathered may be incomplete and subject to future updates.
EE6. European Gender Equality Index (EIGE) – Country score	Average score achieved by each EU country in the EIGE's Gender Equality Index	EIGE's Gender Equality Index, 2024	Lag from last index valuation of 12 months

2. WiD Index Methodology

2.1. Methodology behind the index

The Women in Digital (WiD) Index is a composite indicator designed to measure and track gender equality in the ICT and digital sector across European Union Member States and selected benchmarking countries.

This framework recognizes that achieving gender equality in digital leadership requires addressing barriers and gaps at every stage of the pipeline, from foundational STEM education to senior executive roles. Therefore, the index adopts a pipeline approach, following women's participation from STEM education through to leadership positions in the ICT sector.

For each stage, there is an established underlying weight that will contribute to the general index, as described below:

- **STEM phase (Education) (20% weight):** Foundation for digital pipeline and critical early intervention point:
 - Lays the groundwork for digital literacy and future specialization. Early exposure to STEM subjects increases the likelihood of pursuing ICT-related studies and careers.
 - Critical for shaping interest and confidence. Interventions at this stage can counteract gender biases stereotypes and encourage girls to envision themselves in technical roles. Weight reflects enabling relevance rather than direct participation. The index considers STEM performance as a proxy for potential inclusion in the digital pipeline, acknowledging that many women in STEM do not transition into ICT roles. Encouraging

girls in STEM subjects helps broaden future options, but the impact on ICT participation is indirect and varies by country and education system.

- **ICT phase (Education) (25% weight):** Direct preparation for ICT careers, focusing on specialized skills development:
 - ICT-specific education provides the technical foundation required for entry into digital professions. This phase serves as a transition point where women move from theoretical learning to practical application.
 - The weight reflects how enrolment and completion rates in ICT programs are closely linked to actual employment in the sector, making this phase a targeted indicator of future participation.
- **Digital phase (Employment – Entry to mid-level) (35% weight):** Core career phase, reflects employment reality:
 - Includes key metrics that directly influence long-term career trajectories. Factors like the gender pay gap and access to vocational training shape women’s retention and growth in the sector.
 - The weight reflects both scale and strategic importance. As the largest segment of the workforce, this phase offers the most actionable insights for policy and organizational change. Entry to mid-level roles are pivotal for career development; these stages often determine whether women continue in ICT careers or exit due to lack of support, advancement opportunities, or inclusive environments.
- **Leadership (10% weight):** Career culmination; leadership roles are critical for shaping organizational culture, driving innovation, and influencing policy within ICT and digital:

- Women in senior positions serve as role models, helping to break down stereotypes and inspire younger generations to pursue and persist in ICT and digital careers.
- While the importance of this phase is acknowledged, the lack of consistent, cross-country comparable data on women’s leadership in ICT necessitated a lower weighting. Given the scarcity of harmonized and comparable datasets, this phase relies heavily on survey-based insights from the 2025 Women in Digital survey, which while valuable, carry inherent limitations in representativeness (check paragraphs 2.2.2. Primary sources: Women in Digital Survey and , 3.1. Primary Data Limitations for further details and survey sample, limitations and mitigation strategies).
- **Enabling Environment (10% weight):** Contextual factors; supportive but not deterministic:
 - This phase aims to capture the broader socio-economic and policy context, including factors such as women unemployment rate and contractual conditions. This component helps identify systemic issues that may hinder women’s digital inclusion, even when educational and employment opportunities are available. While these conditions influence women’s ability to enter and remain in digital careers, they are not direct measures of individual engagement.
 - The lower weight reflects its essential but indirect role. The enabling environment is a necessary backdrop for equitable participation, but its impact on the Women in Digital pipeline is mediated through other phases like ICT education and digital employment.

Furthermore, each indicator (as described on chapter 1.1.2) was also assigned a weight within the pillars to determine its representation (Table 6).

Table 6 Overview of metric weightings and normalization approaches

Pillar	Pillar Weight in WiD Index	Metric Code	Metric Name	Metric Weight in Pillar	Normalization Direction
STEM Education	20%	ST1	Girls performance in PISA science across countries	35% Reflects readiness and capabilities to pursue STEM.	Higher is better.
STEM Education		ST2	Girls performance in PISA math across countries	35% Reflects readiness and capabilities to pursue STEM.	Higher is better
STEM Education		ST3	Girls' performance in PISA Science relative to boys	5% Ensures gender equity is acknowledged but doesn't overshadow actual performance levels.	Higher is better
STEM Education		ST4	Girls' performance in PISA Math	5%	Higher is better

Pillar	Pillar Weight in WiD Index	Metric Code	Metric Name	Metric Weight in Pillar	Normalization Direction
			relative to boys	Ensures gender equity is acknowledged but doesn't overshadow actual performance levels.	
STEM Education		ST5	Participation in upper secondary STEM vocational programs	20% Reflects a critical pathway for developing technical STEM skills and preparing students for direct entry into the STEM workforce, including ICT. Not available in each country.	Higher is better
ICT Education	25%	IT1	% Women ICT Bachelor graduates	40% Reflects largest pool, key entry point into ICT careers	Higher is better
ICT Education		IT2	% Women ICT Master graduates	30% Reflects importance for specialization and retention	Higher is better
ICT Education		IT3	% Women ICT PhD graduates	20% Reflects strategic nature for research and innovation	Higher is better
ICT Education		IT4	% Women ICT related	10%	Higher is better

Pillar	Pillar Weight in WiD Index	Metric Code	Metric Name	Metric Weight in Pillar	Normalization Direction
			post secondary IVET	Alternative pathway, presence varies by country	
Digital Phase	35%	DG1	% Employed women with ICT education	10% Reflects entry-level employability	Higher is better
Digital Phase		DG2	% Women ICT specialists	40% Reflects core workforce representation	Higher is better
Digital Phase		DG7	% Women in ICT continuous vocational trainings	15% Reflects career sustainability	Higher is better
Digital Phase		DG8	Perception of Gender Pay Gap	10% Reflects social and psychological barrier to equity	Lower is better (inverted)
Digital Phase		DG5	Actual Gender pay	25% Reflects actual economic equity	Lower is better (inverted)

Pillar	Pillar Weight in WiD Index	Metric Code	Metric Name	Metric Weight in Pillar	Normalization Direction
			gap in ICT (inverted)		
Leadership Phase	10%	LD1	Time taken for women to reach leadership positions	15% Reflects the speed of career progression for women in ICT and partial influence of systemic barriers and equitable opportunities	Lower is better (inverted)
Leadership Phase		LD2	% Women in technical leadership roles	40% Reflects greater inclusion of women in ICT decision-making positions and signals progress toward gender parity in ICT leadership (director level and above)	Higher is better
Leadership Phase		LD3	Average % women in leadership roles (director level+)	15% Expands focus beyond executive roles to broader leadership representation in ICT, reflecting the cultural and structural conditions that support women's advancement in the sector.	Higher is better
Leadership Phase		LD4	Key long-term inhibitors to	30%	Lower is better (inverted)

Pillar	Pillar Weight in WiD Index	Metric Code	Metric Name	Metric Weight in Pillar	Normalization Direction
			ICT leadership	Reflects the importance of perceived structural and cultural barriers to women underrepresentation in ICT leadership	
Enabling Environment	10%	EE1	Women with basic or above basic digital skills	20% Reflects overall women's readiness to participate in the digital economy	Higher is better
Enabling Environment		EE2	Women currently unemployed	15% Provides a baseline for overall labour market inclusivity for women entering ICT	Lower is better (inverted)
Enabling Environment		EE3	Women with children employment rate	15% Captures the impact of caregiving on total women employment	Higher is better
Enabling Environment		EE4	Contractual conditions of women	10% Reflects the quality and stability of employment for women, as one of several structural factors influencing women's participation in the job market	Higher is better

Pillar	Pillar Weight in WiD Index	Metric Code	Metric Name	Metric Weight in Pillar	Normalization Direction
Enabling Environment		EE5	Member State Monitoring - Policy initiative score	10% Measures government action on gender equality in ICT (proactive policy environment)	Higher is better
Enabling Environment		EE6	European Gender Equality Index	30% Provides a comprehensive view of gender equality across domains, shaping the overall context for women's ICT participation	Higher is better

Weighting Definitions

Weights were established through a combination of expert consultation with gender equality and ICT policy specialists, stakeholder feedback from industry representatives and policymakers, statistical analysis of metric correlations and factor loadings and sensitivity testing of alternative weight scenarios.

The weighting of metrics and pillars in the WiD Index was designed to accurately reflect the ICT career pipeline—from education to employment and leadership. For instance, while STEM education is foundational, it received a lower weight than ICT-specific education, which more directly equips women with professional skills relevant to the sector. Within the scope of Connecting Women in Digital, the Digital phase (early to mid-career) is pivotal for expanding women's participation, whereas the Leadership

phase, though important for visibility and role models, depends on broader inclusion earlier in the pipeline. The index reflects a consensus built on research, balancing strengths, data transparency, and limitations, and remains open to new insights and perspectives for future iterations.

2.1.1. Index Construction Methodology

Here below is summarized the four-step process followed to build the Women in Digital Index, from metric selection to quality control:

- **Step 1: Metric Selection and Data Collection:** Identification of quantitative metrics for each pillar based on data availability and policy relevance. Collection of data from multiple sources (secondary statistics and primary survey). Quality assurance and validation of data points.
- **Step 2: Normalization** - Application of min-max normalization to standardise all metrics to a 0-100 scale. Directional adjustment for metrics where lower values indicate better performance.
- Rationale behind the normalization - The WiD Index employs min-max normalization to address several methodological challenges:
 - **Scale Harmonization:** Metrics are measured in different units (percentages, scores, years)
 - **Comparability:** Enables meaningful aggregation across diverse indicators
 - **Interpretability:** Produces 0-100 scale scores that are intuitive for policymakers and enable relative positioning of each EU Member State against one another.
 - **Temporal Stability:** Maintains consistent interpretation over time

- **Step 3: Aggregation** - Calculation of pillar scores using weighted averages of component metrics. Computation of final index scores using pillar weights
- **Step 4: Validation and Quality Control** - Cross-validation of results against known country performance patterns. Sensitivity analysis of weight variations.

2.1.2. Index Calculation Process

Below is a detailed overview of the index calculation process, starting from each metric and leading to the final scoring:

- **Metric Normalization:** Each raw metric value is converted to a 0-100 scale using min-max normalization where the maximum and minimum score across all EU Member States compose the range of analysis.
- **Phase Score Calculation:** Each phase score is computed as a weighted average of its component metrics. Some metrics as indicated on Table 7 have an inverted value, where the lowest score means a higher score. These differences were taken into account when calculating each pillar.
- **Final Index Calculation:** The overall index score combines all phase scores using phase-level weights.

2.1.2.1. Detailed Calculation Example

To illustrate the step by step of the index building, find below the real calculation process for Sweden:

Table 7 Example of Index calculation methodology: Sweden

Metric	EU Min	EU Max	Sweden Value	Normalization Direction
ST1 Girls performance in PISA Science across countries	428.17	527.7	497.80	Higher is better
ST2 Girls performance in PISA Math across countries	420.3	506.7	480.60	Higher is better
ST3 Girls' performance in PISA Science relative to boys	-11.4	28.8	8.36	Higher is better
ST4 Girls' performance in PISA Math relative to boys	-21.1	15.7	-2.20	Higher is better
ST5 Participation in upper secondary STEM vocational programs	1.4	32.26	15.00	Higher is better
IT1 % Women ICT Bachelor	11	39.7	39.70	Higher is better
IT2 % Women ICT Master	17.8	46.9	44.10	Higher is better
IT3 % Women ICT PhD	13.5	38.1	35.60	Higher is better

Metric	EU Min	EU Max	Sweden Value	Normalization Direction
IT4 % Women ICT related post secondary IVET	4	40	25.20	Higher is better
DG1 % Employed women with ICT education	8	31.8	28.80	Higher is better
DG2 % Women ICT specialists	13	27.6	24.00	Higher is better
DG3 Women in ICT continuous vocational trainings	65	100	95.80	Higher is better
DG8 Perception of Gender Pay Gap	10	37.8	25.20	Lower is better (inverted)
DG5 Actual Gender pay gap in ICT (inverted)	6.5	30.2	10.80	Lower is better (inverted)
LD0 Years to reach executive role (survey)	1.5	15	8.50	Lower is better (inverted)
LD1 % Women in ICT leadership roles	1	30	24.40	Higher is better

Metric	EU Min	EU Max	Sweden Value	Normalization Direction
LD3 Average % Women in leadership roles (director level and above) in ICT companies	17.6	33.3	25.70	Higher is better
LD.4 Key long-term inhibitors to ICT leadership	67.3	83.3	76.50	Lower is better (inverted)
EE1. Women with basic or above basic overall digital skills	31.7	88	68.20	Higher is better
EE2. Women currently unemployed	2.89	14.16	7.84	Lower is better (inverted)
EE3. Women with children employment rate	45.4	85.3	85.30	Higher is better
EE4. Contractual conditions of women	29.9	49.3	42.70	Higher is better
EE5 Member State Monitoring - Policy initiative score	0	54	34.00	Higher is better

Metric		EU Min	EU Max	Sweden Value	Normalization Direction
EE6	European Gender equality Index	57.5	82	82.00	Higher is better

Sweden Phase Scores (calculated from weighted metric averages):

- **STEM Education: 62.8** (aggregated ST1, ST2, ST3, ST4 and ST5 scores)
- **ICT Education: 91.0** (aggregated IT1, IT2, IT3 and IT4 scores)
- **Digital Phase: 77.07** (aggregated DG1, DG2, DG3, DG4 and DG5 scores)
- **Leadership: 60.0** (aggregated , LD1, LD2, LD3 and LD4 scores)
- **Enabling Environment: 79.3** (aggregated EE1, EE2, EE3, EE4, EE5 and EE6 scores)

Final Index Calculation:

- STEM: $62.8 * \text{weight on general index of } 0.20 = 12.55$
- ICT: $91.0 * \text{weight on general index of } 0.25 = 22.74$
- Digital Phase: $77.07 * \text{weight on general index of } 0.35 = 26.97$
- Leadership: $59.99 * \text{weight on general index of } 0.10 = 5.99$
- Enabling: $79.27 * \text{weight on general index of } 0.10 = 7.93$
- Total WiD Index Score: 76.2

2.1.2.2. Missing Data Handling

- Within-Phase Missing Data: When individual metrics are unavailable for a country, the phase score is calculated using only available metrics, with weights proportionally adjusted to sum to 100%.

- **Phase-Level Missing Data:** If an entire phase cannot be calculated due to insufficient data, the final index is computed using the remaining pillars with proportionally adjusted weights. This applies specifically to selected benchmarking countries.
- **Quality Indicators:** Countries with significant missing data are flagged in the index results with appropriate caveats about interpretation reliability.

2.2. Main data sources behind the WiD Index

2.2.1. Secondary data

The WiD Index relies substantially on secondary data to benchmark Member States and selected countries on the participation and progression of women in STEM and digital careers. This chapter details the origins, characteristics, and limitations of the secondary data sources used in the Index.

Secondary data consists of statistics and datasets collected by established organizations, primarily:

- **Eurostat:** The main source for education, employment, and digital skills indicators, providing harmonized EU-wide statistics such as:
 - Women's share of ICT graduates at different levels (Bachelor, Master, PhD)
 - Employment rates, contractual conditions, and participation in ICT or digital sectors
 - Gender pay gap calculations specific to ICT roles
 - Digital skills competency rates

- **OECD PISA Scores:** For standardized math and science results by gender at grade 8, fundamental for assessing early engagement and achievement in STEM.
- **Eurostat Labour Force Survey:** Supplementary indicators on women's employment, unemployment, and work conditions.
- **Connecting Women in Digital, D2.1 Overview of national actions - National policy initiative reviews:** Used for scoring the Member State Policy Initiative Score, derived from systematic country-by-country reviews and assessments.
- **The Gender Equality Index (EIGE):** Evaluates gender equality across EU Member States, focusing on critical domains such as work, money, knowledge, time, power, and health. This index is widely used to track progress, highlight disparities, and inform policy decisions at the national and EU levels, and served as benchmarking resource for the enabling environment pillar of WiD.

2.2.2. Primary sources: Women in Digital Survey

The primary data for the Women in Digital Index (WiD Index) includes results from the 2025 WIDCON survey, a foundational source for capturing first-hand insights on women's participation, retention, barriers, and advancement within ICT and digital roles across EU Member States. This section describes the survey design, sample structure, country distribution, respondent types, and the key metrics derived for the WiD Index.

2.2.2.1. Survey Design and Sample Structure

The WIDCON survey was conducted in July 2025 using computer-assisted web interviewing (CAWI), targeting individuals aged 18–74 working in IT/digital roles within companies of 50+ employees across the EU, including both employed and self-

employed participants. The total unweighted sample consists of 4,454 respondents, ensuring coverage across a broad range of industries from software services to manufacturing, government, education, and healthcare. The survey is quantitative, enabling robust benchmarking at the country level.

- **Gender Breakdown:** 54.6% women, 45.4% men, reflecting a deliberate oversampling of female ICT professionals for comparative analyses.
- **Employment Status:** 91.3% employed, 8.7% freelance/self-employed/business owners.
- **Seniority and Role:** All respondents confirm employed or self-employed status in digital/IT roles, and the questionnaire collects data on career breaks, managerial responsibilities, upskilling, career progression, and leadership experience.
- **Company Size Distribution:** A mix of small to large enterprises ensures diversity in workplace contexts.

Country Representation and Sample Coverage

The survey sample spans all EU Member States, with country counts ranging from larger economies (Germany: 628, France: 415, Italy: 426) to smaller samples for less populous countries (Malta: 24, Estonia: 33). This ensures that national data is robust for larger countries and provides useful trend data for smaller ones. The sample size allows for reliable country-level comparisons within the Index.

Types of Respondents

Respondents include full-time and part-time employees, freelancers, and business owners/self-employed across ICT and digital functions. Industry segments covered include:

- Financial services
- Healthcare
- Telecommunications
- Software & Information Services (largest segment at 28.8%)
- Government, education, energy, manufacturing, and retail

Survey-Derived Metrics for WiD Index

A number of key Index metrics are derived directly from the survey, in areas where primary insights are essential or secondary data is unavailable:

Digital Phase Metrics:

- DG3. Women in ICT continuous vocational trainings (CVET): Proportion of women participating in ICT-focused upskilling and reskilling programs (indicative of retention and advancement opportunities).
- DG4. Perception of gender pay gap in ICT: The share of women reporting pay disparity as a challenge to progression (capturing barriers from women's perspective).

Leadership Phase Metrics:

- LD1 Time to reach leadership: Average duration, in years, from entry to ICT leadership roles (extracted from questions on career trajectories).
- LD2. Women in ICT technical leadership roles: Proportion of women in director-level and above ICT positions (calculated using direct survey responses on role and seniority).
- LD3. Women in leadership in ICT companies: Average share of women holding director/executive roles in respondent organizations (direct organization-level reporting).
- LD4. Key long-term inhibitors to ICT leadership: Combined share of respondents highlighting major barriers including work-life balance, advancement opportunities, and upskilling access.

Other Metrics:

- The metric “EE5 Member State Monitoring - Policy initiative score” is linked to results from [D2.1 Overview of National Actions](#), which helped us to understand the level of EU funded investments to mitigate gender inequality in the digital sector across Member States. Additionally, the WiD index leveraged country scores from the European Gender Equality Index (EIGE) (EE6) to represent inequality factors beyond ICT that could impact on career, educational and overall development opportunities for women across Member States. Both metrics were inserted in the enabling environment pillar.

2.3. Inclusion of Benchmarked countries (Brazil, UK, India and USA)

The core objective for incorporating benchmarked countries— United States, India, and Brazil - alongside EU Member States, was to contextualize EU progress against global

leaders or regions with substantial technology sectors and varying gender diversity outcomes. This mechanism enhances the policy relevance and interpretability of the Index, allowing stakeholders to identify successful practices or persistent barriers beyond the EU.

2.3.1. Data Integration Method

For benchmarked countries, the Index uses the same phase and metrics as for EU Member States. Integration follows these steps:

- **Metric alignment:** Data points for benchmarked countries are mapped to the Index's metric definitions wherever possible (e.g., girls' PISA science/math performance, percentage of women ICT graduates, survey indicators for pay gap perception).
- **Normalization:** Scores are computed using the min-max normalization formulas based on EU-wide ranges for best comparison with core countries. Where necessary (e.g., lower is better metrics like pay gap), the formula is inverted, ensuring scores for benchmarked countries are comparable on a 0–100 scale.
- **Handling missing data:** If survey or official statistics were unavailable for certain metrics, those aspects were either left blank or marked as proxies, and pillar scores were calculated as averages of available data for each country.
- **Documentation:** All limitations and proxy adaptations are clearly noted in accompanying documentation (Index final data, score tables, and methodological notes)

Important to notice when comparing core index with benchmarked results: Users are advised that direct comparisons between EU Member State results and benchmarked countries may be affected by local educational systems, labour market structures, and survey coverage.

Furthermore, there are notable coverage gaps in certain pillars (e.g., STEM education for India and Leadership data for USA, Brazil and the UK). Making the production of more detailed metrics unfeasible; these are highlighted in the Index scoreboard and explained in the methodology.

3. Limitations and mitigation strategies

3.1. Secondary Data Limitations

The Women in Digital Index (WiD) heavily relies on secondary data from established statistical sources such as Eurostat, OECD/PISA, and other national or supranational databases to construct its country-level scores and pillars. While these sources confer credibility and ensure international comparability, there are notable limitations affecting both the comprehensiveness and the granularity of the Index.

First, **timeliness is a significant constraint**. Most large-scale statistics, such as those from Eurostat or PISA, are not released instantly but often come with a considerable lag (typically 18-36 months post-collection), meaning the metrics may not reflect the most current conditions or recent policy changes. For fast-evolving fields like digital skills and workforce participation, this lag can obscure emerging trends or newly implemented initiatives.

Second, **coverage and harmonization present methodological challenges**. While Eurostat and OECD strive for alignment, definitions of ICT education, STEM pathways, and digital professions can diverge subtly between countries due to differences in education systems, national classifications, or reporting standards. For instance, what qualifies as a STEM vocational program or as an "ICT specialist" may vary, impacting cross-national comparability and the accuracy of benchmarking.

Third, **data completeness and gaps limit analysis at both metric and country levels**. Not all Member States report every relevant indicator every year, leading to missing data for some countries or metrics. Methods such as proxy estimation or

averaging available metrics help fill gaps, but these can dilute the precision and reliability of the final Index scores.

Fourth, **granularity is constrained to the level of aggregation provided by public sources**. Most indicators are available only at national, rather than regional, city, or sector levels, hindering more nuanced analysis of disparities—for example, inside regions or economic sectors with significant gender gaps.

Finally, **limitations in intersectionality must be acknowledged**. Most secondary sources used for the WiD Index offer breakdowns by gender, but rarely by additional axes of differentiations such as ethnicity, migrantion/citizenship status, sexual orientation, disability, socio-economic status or geographical location or income group. These omitted variables can mask structural deeper inequalities and restrict the Index’s ability to guide targeted interventions. Despite rigorous normalization and methodological triangulation, these limitations require users to interpret WiD Index findings with caution—particularly for time-sensitive policymaking or highly detailed cross-country comparisons.

3.2. Primary Data Limitations

The primary data used in the WiD Index—which comes mainly from the IDC Women in Digital Survey (2025)—offers unique strengths by capturing lived experiences and finer details not available in secondary statistics. However, these advantages come with their own methodological constraints that must be considered in interpreting survey-derived metrics.

Representativeness is a core concern. While the survey achieved a sizable sample of 4,454 respondents across EU Member States, recruitment focused on workers aged 18-74 employed in companies with 50+ employees or self-employed in ICT/digital

roles. This means it omits those in micro-enterprises or informal sectors and may under-represent the most marginalized women, such as those with internationally outsourced contracts or in precarious employment.

Sampling and response bias affect the accuracy of findings. Despite quotas by country, sector, and role, variations in survey participation rates may skew the data: countries or sectors with higher engagement may appear to perform better in leadership or training uptake simply due to more responses. Additionally, self-selection and willingness to report sensitive issues such as discrimination, career breaks, or pay gaps could introduce bias into metrics that rely on subjective experiences.

Recall and interpretation bias can arise, especially for retrospective questions (e.g., the time taken to reach executive roles, perceptions of workplace climate, or experiences with gender-specific challenges). Respondents may unintentionally misestimate durations, underreport hardships, or interpret questions differently depending on cultural or organizational context.

Data granularity and consistency are partially limited by survey design. While the survey instruments allow for multi-faceted breakdowns (e.g., by gender, company size, seniority), practical limits on sample sizes mean that certain subgroups (especially smaller countries or sectors) are marked with asterisks to denote caution due to low statistical significance. The ability to disaggregate beyond core categories is thus constrained.

The dynamic nature of the digital workforce means that survey findings can quickly become outdated as labor market trends, organizational practices, and policy measures evolve. Unlike continuous administrative datasets, surveys provide only snapshots that may fluctuate with timing and external events.

Response authenticity (while surveyed responses are anonymized and confidential) remains a challenge for sensitive themes such as discrimination, pay gaps, or stereotypes. Social desirability bias may influence responses, sometimes resulting in underreporting of negative experiences.

Intersectionality considerations: A further limitation of the primary data lies in its limited integration of an intersectional perspective. While the survey captures gendered experiences within ICT and digital roles, it does not systematically account for how gender intersects with other identity factors, including race, ethnicity, disability, migration background, sexual orientation, socio-economic status, or geographical location. As a result, the WiD Index may not fully reflect the diversity of women's experiences or identify compounded barriers faced by historically marginalized groups. The binary categorization of gender also constrains the inclusion of non-binary and gender-diverse individuals. Recognizing these gaps, future iterations of the WiD Index will aim to incorporate a more intersectionally sensitive lens, collecting insights through consultations with diverse stakeholders via the WiD Forum to ensure a broader understanding of women's realities in digital education and employment.

Leadership phase scoring: There are currently no widely available, standardized official statistics on digital leadership disaggregated by gender at the EU and Member State level that can serve as a consistent, comparable source. Most national statistical offices lack sufficiently detailed and up-to-date data, and private sector data is often inaccessible or not harmonized, resulting in significant gaps in coverage and consistency. As a result, the 2025 Women in Digital Survey serves as the primary data source for the metrics included in the Leadership phase of the Women in Digital Index. However, as previously mentioned, relying on primary research data introduces several inherent limitations, including:

- Limitations due to data subjectivity: Survey responses can be influenced by recall bias, especially on sensitive topics such as the glass ceiling or barriers to career progression.
- Limitations due to sample size: Especially in smaller countries surveyed, the proportion of women respondents in senior ICT positions can be limited to support robust cross-country comparisons. For this reason, results for these countries are marked with an asterisk in D2.2 Women in Digital and Foundational Survey Findings and should be interpreted with caution.

While the leadership phase is recognized as a critical component of the digital career journey, especially given its role in shaping organizational culture and providing visible role models, the 10% weighting reflects both its strategic importance and the practical constraints in data availability.

The reliance on primary data from the 2025 Women in Digital Survey, though valuable, introduces limitations in consistency and comparability across countries. As such, leadership indicators in the WiD Index are best used to identify broad trends and gaps rather than to provide a definitive or exhaustive picture of women's representation in ICT leadership across Europe.

Given these factors, while primary data enriches the WiD Index and enables unique insights, it should complement rather than replace secondary data and should be interpreted considering these inherent limitations.

3.3.Mitigation strategies

Efficient data collection and reliable metric reporting are vital for the robustness of subsequent WiD Index releases. Lessons from the 2025 methodological cycle reveal several areas of attention for future iterations:

Enhance Data Coverage and Consistency:

- Maintain standardisation of data definitions and sources to ensure comparability, especially across metrics using Eurostat and PISA. Harmonizing educational stage definitions, job classifications, and contract categories across Member States will help minimize mismatches and improve trend analyses.
- Expand primary data efforts for hard-to-capture populations by refining survey sampling frameworks in underrepresented segments (e.g., smaller EU nations, freelancers, non-traditional ICT sectors). Utilize stratified sampling and quota controls to secure representative cross-country perspectives, particularly for leadership and enabling environment pillars.
- Broaden secondary data partnerships. Collaborate directly with national statistical offices, labour agencies, and academic institutions to access micro-data where Eurostat or OECD/PISA reporting is lagging or incomplete, especially for STEM IVET and advanced degree statistics.

Address Timeliness and Frequency Challenges:

- Align data collection cycles with major reporting bodies. Time survey launches to precede public Eurostat/OECD data releases; wherever possible, supplement lagging indicators with rapid survey waves or proxy variables to ensure results reflect the most current reality.
- Utilize longitudinal data and panel designs in proprietary surveys to track drops and improvements in women's ICT participation and leadership over time, compensating for infrequent updates from public sources.

Strengthen Data Validity and Quality:

- Repeat data validation through triangulation and cross-referencing at every cycle. Cross-check key indicators against multiple datasets (e.g., Eurostat, survey findings, and national ministries) to confirm accuracy and highlight discrepancies, particularly for contentious metrics such as gender pay gap and contract quality.
- Peer review and transparent reporting. Submit survey instruments and analytical frameworks to external experts prior to launch; provide methodological summaries with caveats for user interpretation, including sample bias and limitations notes.

Mitigate Survey Design and Response Bias

- Refine questionnaire language and piloting for every new iteration. Use iterative pre-testing in different national contexts to remove ambiguities, ensure terminology aligns with respondent backgrounds, and reduce social desirability bias. Pilot difficult questions (like perceptions of pay gap and leadership inhibitors) and adjust for local sensitivities.
- Apply weighting schemes post-survey. If observed response rates skew by company size, sector, or demographic, use post-stratification weights based on known labour force statistics to correct results and better represent the ICT workforce composition across countries.

Facilitate Policy and Stakeholder Feedback

- Continue to formalise feedback loops with country-level stakeholders. Establish annual workshops or focus groups with teachers, company HR leads, women's STEM organizations, and government representatives to review limitations of current reporting and co-design metrics for emerging priorities (e.g., digital skills bootcamps, flexible ICT pathways).
- Share preliminary findings for comment. Repeat Circulation of draft Index results to national policymakers and women's advocacy groups and request feedback to identify blind spots, contextual challenges, or data anomalies that may not be apparent from aggregated statistics.

4. Women in Digital Dashboards

The WiD Index data included in D2.2 WiD index foundational data and survey findings can be accessed online at <https://index.widigital.eu/index/> through interactive dashboards. The aim of the dashboard is to transform static data into an engaging, accessible, and actionable resource. Beyond functionality, interactive dashboards can improve accessibility and engagement. By presenting data in a clear and easy-to-navigate format, they allow a wider range of stakeholders to explore and interpret information effectively. This interactivity empowers stakeholders to identify trends and identify gaps and best performances, compare countries, and track progress along the pipeline, fostering transparency and informed policy-making.

The dashboards were officially launched on November 14 during the WiD Digital Summit in Brussels, giving participants access to explore and engage with the Index results on the same day. The dashboards will be updated in 2026, following the release of the updated WiD Index in D2.3 – WiD Index Foundational Data and Survey Findings V2.

Users can access a table showing aggregated and total scores for each country and the EU average (Figure 2), ranked by total overall performers. Average scores for EU are highlighted in bold.

Figure 2 The WiD Country Ranking Table View

Country	STEM Education Score	ICT Education Score	Digital Employment Score	Leadership Score	Enabling Environment Score	Final Score
Sweden	62.8	91.0	77.1	60.0	79.3	76.2
Estonia*	85.6	65.1	71.2	47.8	49.0	68.0
Ireland	73.7	63.4	66.7	71.1	69.6	68.0
Finland	78.0	53.1	63.2	61.3	76.1	64.8
Latvia*	54.0	52.8	69.8	42.8	46.5	57.4
Denmark	61.2	46.8	61.4	44.1	71.9	57.0
Romania	17.8	74.5	75.9	54.0	27.0	56.8
Spain	52.5	26.7	75.3	55.9	54.2	54.5
Belgium	65.9	20.0	57.0	74.6	63.7	52.8
Bulgaria	27.6	71.1	59.1	49.7	43.2	52.8
France	55.5	36.9	54.8	67.9	63.9	52.7
Austria	52.3	31.4	58.0	75.3	64.4	52.6
Portugal	46.4	50.2	58.5	39.8	57.8	52.1
Netherlands	60.0	33.7	52.4	59.1	73.1	52.0
EU Average	53.9	44.6	54.6	53.3	54.5	51.7
Slovenia*	70.4	31.3	54.3	40.9	57.6	50.8
Croatia*	53.9	48.5	54.4	44.4	43.3	50.7
United Kingdom **	59.8	37.7	54.8		41.6	50.4
India **		66.1	79.8	10.3	15.0	50.0

Source: [Index - Women In Digital Index](#)

Dashboard visualizations also allow to consult data using two main filters:

- By phase
- By country

The phase filter allows stakeholders to quickly compare country performance based on overall scores for each phase, while the country filter provides a detailed view of individual metrics and values for a selected country. This enables the identification of gaps and areas of best performance at a more granular level.

4.1. Dashboard visualizations by phase

Dashboard visualizations in the form of bar charts by phase allow users to view score rankings by the best-performing countries, broken down by stages along the WiD pipeline (STEM, Digital, ICT, Leadership, Enabling Environment) as well as the overall score (Final Index) (Figure 3).

Users can seamlessly switch between these views by clicking on the buttons with the name of each phase.

Figure 3 Country performance by phase - Final score example

Source: [Index - Women In Digital Index](#)

Figure 4 Country performance by phase – STEM phase example

Source: [Index - Women In Digital Index](#)

4.2. Dashboard visualizations by country

From the same webpage featuring the WiD Country Ranking table with overall scores and the bar charts by phase, users can also access detailed results at the individual country level for all the EU27 member states and benchmarking countries (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Results by country view

Source: [Index - Women In Digital Index](#);

By clicking the "Read more" button, users are directed to a new page that provides a detailed overview of metrics and data for the selected country.

This page includes a summary view comparing the country's performance against the EU average by total score for each phase, presented in a spider chart (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Results by country - Sweden example

WOMEN IN DIGITAL COUNTRY SCORE

Source: [Sweden - Women In Digital Index](#)

On the same page, users can also view the values obtained by each country for every individual metric within each phase, presented in a tabular format. This table includes the complete list of metrics that make up the Index (see paragraph 1.1.2.1), along with the minimum and maximum recorded values for each metric across the EU27 and benchmarking countries for comparison (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Metrics for each phase by country - Sweden example

STEM Education Phase				
Metric	EU Min	Value	EU Max	Unit
ST1 Girls performance in PISA science across countries	428.17	497.8	527.7	Average score, unit
ST2 Girls performance in PISA math across countries	420.3	480.6	506.7	Average score, unit
ST3 Girls' performance in PISA Science relative to boys	-11.4	8.4	28.8	Points difference (Girls - Boys)
ST4 Girls' performance in PISA Math relative to boys	-21.1	-2.2	15.7	Points difference (Girls - Boys)
ST5 Participation in upper secondary STEM vocational programs	1.4	15	32.26	%
Total Score		62.8		
ICT Phase				
Metric	EU Min	Value	EU Max	Unit
IT1 Women ICT graduates (ISCED Level 6)	11	39.7	39.7	%
IT2 Women with an ICT master of science (ISCED Level 7)	17.8	44.1	46.9	%
IT3 Women with a PhD in ICT-related fields (ISCED Level 8)	13.5	35.6	38.1	%
IT4 Women enrolled in ICT-related post secondary IVET	4	25.2	40	%
Total Score		91		
Digital Phase				
Metric	EU Min	Value	EU Max	Unit
DG1 Employed women with an ICT education	8	28.8	31.8	%
DG2 Women ICT specialists	13	24.0	27.6	%
DG3 Women in ICT continuous vocational trainings	65	95.8	100	%
DG4 Perception of Gender Pay Gap	10	25.2	37.8	%
DG5 Actual Gender pay gap in ICT	6.5	10.8	30.2	% gap
Total Score		77.1		

Source: [Sweden - Women In Digital Index](#)

Comparing each country's metric values with the minimum and maximum recorded across the EU27 and benchmarking countries is essential for context and interpretation. Absolute scores alone do not reveal whether a country is performing near the top, bottom, or middle of the spectrum. By showing the range, stakeholders can understand the relative position of each country, identify leaders and laggards, and assess the scale of disparities. This benchmarking approach also highlights areas where improvement is most needed and supports evidence-based policy decisions.

ANNEX 1: Discarded metrics from the WiD Index

Deliverable 1.1, Women in Digital Playbook, presented a preliminary set of metrics proposed for the Women in Digital Index. These metrics were subsequently reviewed during the data collection phase, and some had to be discarded or replaced due to limitations in data availability, consistency, and granularity across countries. In these cases, secondary and primary data for specific digital indicators was either missing, incomplete, or not collected in a sufficiently comparable format. As a result, these metrics were excluded to maintain the overall integrity of the Index:

STEM Phase:

- **Girls' performance in STEM subjects in primary education:** This metric was excluded due to limitations in data comparability and relevance. One of the identified source, TIMSS (IEA) data at the primary level often varies in methodology, curriculum alignment, and coverage across countries, making cross-national comparisons less reliable. Additionally, while TIMSS provides useful insights into early academic achievement, primary education is generally less indicative of future engagement in digital careers or advanced STEM pathways. Research shows that gender gaps in digital skills and attitudes toward technology tend to emerge more clearly during adolescence, when students begin to make educational and career-related choices¹. For this reason, the OECD PISA metric for secondary education was retained. This metric provides more standardised and policy-relevant data on gender performance in STEM

¹ Campos, D. G., & Scherer, R. (2024). Digital gender gaps in students' knowledge, attitudes and skills: an integrative data analysis across 32 countries. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29, 655–693. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12272-9>

subjects at a stage where these gaps are more consequential. Nonetheless, a qualitative analysis of the gender gap in STEM subjects at the primary education level—such as gender diversity among teaching staff—and its potential implications for later educational stages will be part of the discussions within the Connecting Women in Digital thematic working groups.

Leadership Phase:

- **Women on the Board of Directors of top technology companies AND Women CEOs in top technology companies:** This metric was excluded due to data limitations and inconsistencies across countries. To ensure comparability and data availability, the analysis focused on ICT and digital publicly listed companies, which typically provide transparent and standardized data on board composition, in contrast with private entities, where leadership data is not publicly available or consistently reported. However, in several countries, especially those with smaller economies or tech sectors, the number of publicly listed technology firms is extremely limited or non-existent, making it impossible to generate meaningful or representative insights. Given the goal of ensuring full coverage across at least 27 EU member states, metrics with reliable and complete data across the EU geographic scope of the Index were prioritised. Similarly, the metric on Women CEOs in top technology companies was excluded due to the same data limitations affecting board-level representation. To address this gap while maintaining comprehensive coverage, primary data from the Women in Digital proprietary survey was leveraged, by including a metric measuring the share of women at director level and above in ICT companies within the total sample. This alternative provides a comparable snapshot of women in leadership positions across the digital sector, including

private companies, based on a consistent methodology applied across all EU27 countries. Although it does not focus exclusively on CEOs or board members, it provides an equally relevant and broader picture of women's presence in senior decision-making roles, making it an effective indicator of gender balance in digital leadership.

- **Time taken for women to reach leadership positions AND Retention rate of women in ICT executive positions:** These metrics were initially considered for inclusion through the Women in Digital proprietary survey. However, these indicators require a sufficiently large and representative sample at the country level to ensure meaningful and comparable results. In many cases, especially for smaller EU member states, the sample size of surveyed ICT companies was not robust enough to support consistent analysis across EU countries in scope. Additionally, no reliable secondary data sources was identified for these metrics. Most national statistics offices do not track career progression timelines or retention at leadership level by gender, and even when such data exists, it is often aggregated at a high level (e.g. across all industries or job levels), making it unsuitable for targeted analysis of the ICT sector. Furthermore, private companies typically do not publish internal HR metrics such as tenure or promotion timelines, especially disaggregated by gender. These limitations make it extremely difficult to retrieve reliable secondary data for these indicators, as such information is rarely collected or published in a standardized format by national statistics offices or industry bodies. Given these limitations, these metrics were excluded from this first iteration of the Index, to preserve methodological integrity and cross-country comparability. As a mitigation strategy for future iterations, the feasibility of defining quotas for leadership-level positions within the ICT sector in the survey sample is being considered.

ANNEX 2: Full List of Sources

STEM Phase

Source:	Data source:
Eurostat	educ_uae_ent02
OECD	OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), 2022
OECD	Distribution of enrolled students, new entrants and graduates by field of education

ICT Phase

Source:	Data source:
Eurostat	educ_uae_grad10
Ministry of Education, India	AISHE (All India Survey on Higher Education), 2022
OECD	Distribution of enrolled students, new entrants and graduates by field of education

Digital Phase

Source:	Data source:
Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE)	Women in ICT roles
Eurostat	isoc_ski_itsex; isoc_sks_itsps; earn_gr_gpgr2
Connecting Women in Digital	Women in Digital proprietary Survey (EU N=4454)
ILOSTAT	Gender pay gap in Information and Communication
National Association of Software and Services Companies (NASSCOM)	Women and IT Scorecard, 2022
OECD	Digital Economy Outlook, 2017
TeamLease Digital	Gender Parity - Shaping Workforce Equity, Tech Contractual Workforce Perspective, 2025

Leadership Phase

Source:	Data source:
Avsar	Bridging the Leadership Gap: Women Leaders Rise in India's IT Sector, 2025
Connecting Women in Digital	Women in Digital proprietary Survey (EU N=4454)

Enabling Environment

Source:	Data source:
Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE)	Employed women with children (up to 6 years old)
Eurostat	eq_dskl07; lfsi_emp_a; lfst_hheredty; lfsa_epgais; isoc_sk_dskl_i21
Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI)	State-wise percentage of persons of age 5 years and above who used internet during the last 30 days
UK Office for National Statistics (ONS)	Female employment rate (aged 16 to 64, seasonally adjusted): %, 2025
Regional Center for Studies on the Development of the Informational Society (Cetic.br) 2024	The State of Meaningful Connectivity in Brazil: Measuring Quality and Revealing Hidden Gaps - Global Digital Inclusion Partnership, 2024
US Bureau of Labor Statistics	Employment Characteristics of Families, 2024; US Full-time Employed Persons: Women, 2023
World Bank	Labor force participation rate, female (% of female population ages 15+) (modelled ILO estimate); Part-time employment, female (% of total female employment)

ANNEX 3 – WiD Survey Sample Structure

By country:

Country	Frequency	Percent
Austria	107	2.4
Belgium	209	4.7
Bulgaria	108	2.4
Croatia	36	0.8
Cyprus	24	0.5
Czech Republic	151	3.4
Denmark	85	1.9
Estonia	33	0.7
Finland	85	1.9
France	415	9.3
Germany	628	14.1
Greece	162	3.6
Hungary	106	2.4
Ireland	76	1.7
Italy	426	9.6
Latvia	31	0.7
Lithuania	39	0.9
Luxembourg	33	0.7
Malta	24	0.5
Netherlands	216	4.8
Poland	402	9
Portugal	162	3.6
Romania	210	4.7
Slovakia	75	1.7
Slovenia	33	0.7
Spain	422	9.5
Sweden	156	3.5
Total	4454	100

By gender:

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Woman	2433	54.6
Man	2021	45.4
Total	4454	100

By age:

Age	Frequency	Percent
18-24 years	388	8.7
25-34 years	1425	32
35-44 years	1445	32.4
45-54 years	809	18.2
55-74 years	387	8.7
Total	4454	100

By company size:

Company Size	Frequency	Percent
50-99 employees	773	17.4
100-499 employees	1366	30.7
500-999 employees	593	13.3
1,000+ employees	1335	30
Freelancer/self-employed/business owner	387	8.7
Total	4454	100

By industry sector:

Sector	Frequency	Percent
Financial Services	503	11.3
Healthcare	463	10.4
Telecommunications	323	7.3
Energy	153	3.4
Manufacturing & Resources	666	15
Retail	180	4
Software & Information Services	1283	28.8
Transportation and Leisure	271	6.1
Business & Personal Services	214	4.8
Education	227	5.1
Government	171	3.8
Total	4454	100